

Peacekeeping Forces Skills as a Solution to Resolve the Israeli–Palestinian Conflict Reviewed From Cross–Cultural Competence & Resilience Perspective

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ABSTRACT: *The conflict that occurred in Israel-Palestine has lasted a very long time. Israel has a society that is very diverse in terms of its social order, starting from different hereditary roots, cultures, and traditions. Palestine has a different ideology, religion, and way of life from Israel. So that it creates a protracted conflict. The Oslo Peace Agreement is a solution to the conflict in Israel-Palestine. When Yitzak Rabin was killed, the agreement ended and gave rise to another negotiation effort as a framework for a two-state solution. The research methods and approaches used are qualitative and literature studies. After analyzing, the results of this study found that when viewed from the historical timeline of the conflict in Israel-Palestine, this conflict has been going on for quite a long time. The categorization that occurs will be a trigger for conflict because there are differences that lead to comparisons between groups which result in stereotypes against other groups. The Garuda contingent carried out a peace mission through a cultural approach in which there was emotional intelligence. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is the result of different cultures and traditions. Peacekeeping forces assigned to Israel-Palestine must have Cultural Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, Social Intelligence, Cross-Cultural Competencies, and Resiliency.*

KEYWORDS –*Israeli-Palestinian conflict, social categorization, Garuda contingent, peacekeeping force*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Palestinian-Israeli conflict has occurred for a very long time, Israel itself has a very diverse society in terms of its social order, starting from the roots of descent, culture, and different traditional tendencies, which in the end their social goals are very diverse (Junardi, 2005).), while Palestine itself, the conflicts that occurred in Palestine-Israel due to differences in ideology, religion, and way of life (Junardi, 2005), all peace efforts have been made, one of which is the implementation of the Oslo Peace Agreement, and in 1993, the Peace Agreement Oslo establishes a framework for Palestine as a state that has its own jurisdiction (Ashed, 2015). Which in the process provides and sets territorial parameters for the Palestinians which will slowly become a territory without the jurisdiction of the state of Israel. The agreement, in essence, was a breakthrough for negotiating the Israeli-Palestinian conflict in the previous decades, because the agreement was able to lead the leader of the Palestine Liberation Organization at the time, Yasser Arafat, to set foot back in his homeland (Ashed, 2015). The Oslo agreement seems to provide hope regarding a possible solution that can be achieved for both Palestine and Israel, namely the two-state solution, to the exclusion of the one-state solution which is widely criticized by various parties (Ashed, 2015).

But in 1995 Yitzak Rabin who was the former Prime Minister of Israel was killed, it made the basis for the termination of the agreement. Then peace efforts were carried out again in 2013-2014 with the holding of a peace talk which is a negotiation conversation that is within the framework of a two-state solution and was initiated by the former US Secretary of State, John Kerry, who is expected to provide a solution to the conflict between Israel and Palestine. But the conversation failed because both parties did not respect each other's "good will". Some of the causes are the Israeli side which continues to expand settlements in the West Side and the joint-cooperation between Hamas and Fatah (BBC, 2014).

Israel's attitude to the solution of all the failures of the 2013-2014 peace talk, has implications for the ownership and arrangement of the Palestinian territories over Israel, which is becoming increasingly clear, so that creating the two desired ones as in previous years, cannot be possible (Najjar 2017). Internal reconciliation between the parties working in Palestine, namely Hamas, which tends to be militant, and Fatah, which is more diplomatic, resulted in the failure of the 2013-2014 peace talks. However, according to the President of the Palestinian Authority (PA), Mahmoud Abbas, the reconciliation does not violate the commitment to the two-state solution peace framework with Israel (BBC 2014). This is a basis that the Peace Keeping Force needs to know in peacekeeping missions that the conflict that occurs, it is seen that there are several cultural differences between Palestine and Israel. In addition, there are also differences in the nature of the Israeli and Palestinian leaders, (Muhamad, 2013) Efforts to revive the peace process can only be carried out, if Israel has a genuine desire to be involved in important issues. For this reason, the international community through the Security Council needs to ensure that Israel respects and complies with various UN resolutions related to the conflict, such as resolutions 242 of 1967, 338 (1973), and 1397 (2002).

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this study is a qualitative research method. In qualitative research, the researcher is the main instrument in collecting and interpreting data, and other tools (if any) are only a tool for the researcher (Hardani, et al., 2020). This study is carried out by reviewing or interpreting written material based on its context. Written material in the form of published notes, textbooks, newspapers, manuscripts, articles and previous similar research. The stages of this research are choosing the topic to be studied, digging up information, determining the focus of the research, collecting data sources, reading data sources, finding relevant theories used to dissect the data obtained, analyzing based on relevant theories and data, and then drawing conclusions and recommendation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this case the researcher will try to conduct a comparative study of the conflicts that have occurred in the RD Congo, where the Garuda Contingent was involved in the UN Peacekeeping Force to the African Congo since the Garuda III Troops in 1962 under the UNOC Mission under the leadership of Brigadier General TNI. Kemal Idris until now Garuda XXXIX-B troops are in Congo with the UN MONUSCO mission under the leadership of Colonel Inf Daniel Lumban Raja. The Garuda troops in their assignment were considered very successful and well received by the Congolese people. The success of the Garuda troops was proven by being able to save the Congolese people from the ferocity of bandits, Congolese robbers, freeing female hostages of US citizens and being able to become agents of peace in the Congo with several Congolese militias willing to make peace by surrendering their weapons to the Garuda troops. So far, the Indo RDB Task Force has succeeded in surrendering 72 ex-combatants and handing over 32 AK-47s, 2 FALs, 1 grenade and 346 live ammunition.

Basically, carrying out a peace mission requires people from various backgrounds to cooperate and work with local residents who they may not know (Rubinstein et al., 2008). The problem, however, is that they face difficulties in connecting with the people in the area where they are stationed, and (vertical interoperability), and ironically, they also face difficulties in cooperating effectively with others serving the mission, both military and civilian (horizontal interoperability) The conflict that occurred in RD Congo was a social conflict that escalated into an ethnic conflict which eventually split into several groups and formed a new

group, namely the Tutsi ethnicity and the Hutu ethnicity, where before the formation of the group a social categorization occurred as follows: said by Turner (in Tajfel, 1982) and Ellemers et al., (2002) revealed that social categories are the division of individuals based on race, class, occupation, gender, religion, and others into a group, by doing social categorization based on race, class, culture, and so on.

This is the basis that someone will enter into smaller groups because of the equality of race, class, and perhaps their thinking or their flexibility, which will eventually result in group and out group as Turner, Giles, said. (1985) and Branscombe et al., (1993). In general, individuals divide the social world into two distinct categories: us and them. We are in group, while they are out group. The categorization that occurs will be a trigger for conflict because there are differences that will often be carried out between groups, where Tajfel and Wilkes (1963) found that division into categories can result in a "tendency to exaggerate the differences... between things. -things that belong to different classes, and to minimize these differences within each class".

For these differences, a person will make comparisons between groups and this becomes the basis for creating stereotypes against other groups regardless of the nature and behavior of their own individuals. Besides, Banaji (2001) shows that the concept of stereotype refers to beliefs, knowledge, expectations of social groups and has been theorized as a cognitive counterpart in the stereotypical prejudice duo since the 1920s and empirically investigated since the 1930s. In this case there will be judgments that come from between groups, especially on their knowledge, and expectations.

The Garuda contingent carried out a peace mission through a cultural approach, from this it is also clear that the quality of emotional intelligence of the Peacekeepers plays an important role, because they can understand the feelings of the people of RD Congo, as Salovey Mayer said (in Goleman, 2001) that Someone with high emotional intelligence will be able to overcome the problems and challenges that arise in his life. The dynamics that occur in leading greatly affect one's emotions, the pressures that come on a leader, will provide evidence of how good the emotions of a leader are. One of the conflicts that the TNI Task Force was able to overcome was that it succeeded in reconciling the conflict that occurred in 2019, a dispute between the Bantu and Twa Tribe groups in Kabwela Village, Tanganyika Province, Democratic Republic of the Congo, resulted in several surrounding villages being burned, causing residents to leave village to seek refuge.

3 people died and 5 of them were injured. One of the villages that was burned down by the Twa Tribe is Kambu Village. In that incident the Commander of the Konga XXXIX-A RDB MONUSCO TNI Task Force Colonel Inf Dwi Sasongko ordered his troops to carry out long-distance patrols using Komodo vehicles, and the TNI Task Force Soldiers led by Captain Inf Agung Sedayu succeeded in bringing together the two warring tribal leaders, namely the Tribal Chief. Bantu was represented by Katuta Wa Katuta (Chief of Fatuma Village), Muyemba Funkwe (Chief of Kambu Village) and the leader of the Twa Tribe was represented by General Kamuti. (Fadillah, 2019). From this incident, it can be seen the quality of the Peacekeepers from Indonesia that the emotional intelligence possessed by the Indonesian peacekeepers is very mature, so that they succeeded in reconciling conflicts that occurred despite a lot of mental pressure, as said by Salovey Mayer in Shapiro, (1997), Someone with high emotional intelligence is judged to be able to control his emotions to face problems when facing something that raises pressure. Then in 2020, there was another conflict between the three tribes in RD Congo, in this case the Indonesian troops used informal channels. The local community there is the same as Indonesia, which prefers the informal route. The commanders tried to find out who the local commanders were, local leaders were then invited to interact in informal ways such as coffee and formal discussions, repairing churches and mosques with local people (Wibowo, 2018), so that Indonesian troops could be more accepted by the local RD Congo people with the aim of blending in with the local people. Community, this is a step by the Garuda Troops who are trying hard to gain the trust of the people of RD Congo, and also proves that the arrival of the Garuda Troops to the conflict area that occurred in RD Congo is not looking for profit and interests.

The Garuda contingent gained the trust of ex-combatant to the TNI Task Force in collaboration with traditional leaders, both the Kaomba perci group, Perci Aleluya group and the Apa Napaledi group in the Area of Responsibility COB Kompi Bravo IndoRDB led by Major Inf Dikdik Sukayat. In addition, the role of the Garuda Contingent, as stated by the TNI Task Force Commander, was that in addition to carrying out the peace mission, Civil Military Coordination (CIMIC) activities were also held which included free health services, field

psychology and a mini library, as well as meetings with tribal chiefs and local traditional leaders. (Iswinaro, 2020)

The success of the Garuda Contingent in overcoming the conflict in the Congo cannot be separated from the expertise of the Peacekeeping Force, where it can be seen that the background of the Garuda Contingent is from Indonesia which is a country rich in culture, customs, religion, race, ethnicity, and so on, as stated by Linton that culture is the whole attitude and pattern of behavior and knowledge which is a habit that is inherited and owned by a member of a particular society. So that it makes it easier for the Garuda Contingent to adapt to conflict situations that occur, because the Garuda Contingent is motivated by a country that has many customs, and cultures, this ultimately supports the emotional intelligence of the TNI Task Force on duty in peace missions in RD Congo, and unconsciously affect the employability of the Garuda Contingent on duty in RD Congo, where Coetzee and Harry (2013, in Schutte et al., 2008) say that emotional intelligence is a person's ability that needs to be considered because it is related to emotional intelligence and one's employability.

According to Fugate, Kinicki, & Ashford, (2004) employability is an individual's ability that enables him to adapt cognitively, behaviorally, and affectively, so as to improve the quality of his work. This work potential which is influenced by emotional intelligence is not possessed by many Peacekeeping Forces, and this has helped the Garuda Contingent so that it can be accepted by the RD Congo community and gain the trust of ex-combatant. Furthermore, the conflict that occurred in the RD Congo itself was because there was a rebel group led by Laurent Kabili who at that time had communism and wanted to overthrow the President of the RD Congo who at that time was led by Mobutu Sese Seko, because his government was considered too pro-American. It also forms a basis that supports the Garuda Contingent in their involvement as a Peacekeeping Force which is quite successful in overcoming the conflict in RD Congo, because the Garuda Contingent comes from the Indonesian state where Indonesia has Pancasila ideology, not communism, or liberalism, in addition. Indonesia is also included in the non-Western region and has a collectivism culture.

The superiority of the Garuda Contingent which has a better cultural approach compared to western culture, because it has a collectivism nature, which considers that the people in conflict are part of their people, as stated by Kim, Triandis, Kagitcibasi, Choi, & Yoon, (1994).), non-Western cultures are usually associated with a "collective" perspective Western cultures are usually associated with an "individualistic" value system. This is an advantage in overcoming the conflicts that occurred in RD Congo and making it easier for the Garuda Contingent to be accepted by the people of RD Congo, and this is also supported by Lund, Morris, and LeBaron-Duryea (1994), who suggest that a culture-centered model that incorporating a culturally sensitive approach to conflict may be more appropriate than the universal ("one size fits all") intervention model, and it is a step in the right direction in addressing the conflict that exists in DR Congo between the Tutsi and the Hutu.

Referring to this opinion, this was also realized by the Garuda Contingent in dealing with the conflict in the RD Congo, with a very positive form of participation, namely during the International Women's Day event, where the Women Peacekeepers of the Konga TNI XXXIX-B RDB MONUSCO Task Force held a service free health care, coloring competitions for children, field games and introducing Indonesian culture in the form of the Kaka Enda Dance which was participated by the Congolese Mama-Mama Association, as well as all residents around the flag COB operation area. On this occasion, the INDO RDB XXXIX-B Task Force in collaboration with Societe Nationale d'Electricite (SNEL) of Tanganyika province carried out a mass dance typical of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Puspen TNI, 2020).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

From the discussion above, it can be concluded that in overcoming a conflict that occurs in a country with cultural differences, as well as the ideology of a country in conflict, there is a need for an adaptation that needs to be carried out by the peacekeeping force in carrying out its peace mission, efforts what has been done in dealing with the conflict that occurred in Palestine-Israel is not much different from the conflict that has occurred in the Congo, where there are ideological differences that occur in the conflict, where in the conflict that occurred in the Congo there are ideological differences between the Rebels, namely Laurent Kabila where

he is a person who has an understanding of communism, while Mobutu Sese Seko, is a person who is considered very close and is considered a puppet from the United States, who has liberalism. Besides that, there are also similarities between the conflicts that occurred in Palestine-Israel, and the conflicts that occurred in the RD Congo, which has a diversity of cultures and different traditions.

4.2 Recommendations

The proposal that can be given in this case, for the Peace Keeping Force who will go to the conflict area between Palestine and Israel, is to put forward a cultural approach, by focusing the troops on studying the cultures that exist both in Palestine, and also Israel, Cultural Intelligence has an important role in overcoming conflicts that occur so that the Peace Keeping Force can be well received in the conflict area, besides that the power of Emotional Intelligence also cannot be ruled out, because it is an inseparable part of each individual Peacekeeping Force. will be dispatched to the Palestinian-Israeli Conflict area, from these two things, training can be carried out in advance to make it easier for the Peace Keeping Force to socialize so as to create a negotiation, good mediation of the conflict that occurs, these two important points become the basis for Peace Keeping Force to have Social Intelligent in overcoming problems that occur in the Palestinian-Israeli Conflict. So that the Peace Keeping Force has Cross-Cultural Competencies and Resiliency.

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